

scald was higher in the cultivars of the lot seeded on 13 June than in those of the lot seeded 23 June; the trend was similar for the check variety LAC23 (see table). Although no information on weather parameters was recorded, the differences in disease incidence have been due to environmental factors. Fertilizer application increased disease incidence in resistant, moderately susceptible, and susceptible varieties seeded on both dates. Closer spacing did not affect leaf scald incidence.

Observed as resistant were 63–83, M202, D4-135, Moroberekan, Peroda, ROK 3, C46-153, and the locally bred upland lines LS(1)-29-2-NI 2, LS(1)-1-1-NI 3, LS(25)-4-1-NI 1, LS(25)-4-1-NI 4, TOX 95-8-1-1-LS 2, TOX 95-8-1-1-LS 3, TOX 95-8-1-4-LS 5, TOX 95-8-1-4-LS 6, and TOX 95-8-1-5-10.

Susceptible cultivars were Juma 1, M10, TOS 2581, TOS4113, TOS 4169, IR1746-194-1-1-1, IR2737-F4B-1-3-1, IR1754-F5B-16, BPI 76/Bicol, Binotas M1-48, E 425, T19, IR1746-226-1-2-2, IR841-671-2-2-1-2, and IR2053-522-5.

Moderately susceptible cultivars were

Incidence of leaf scald on rice cultivars seeded on different dates with different fertilizer and spacing rates. Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko, Liberia.

Varietal group	Lines (no.)	Seeding date	Disease score ^a				Mean
			0 NPK at		40-40-40 NPK at		
			30 cm	15 cm	30 cm	15 cm	
Resistant ^b	4	13 June	2.8	2.8	3.0	3.0	2.9
	23	23 June	1.2	1.1	2.8	2.9	2.0
Moderately susceptible ^c	66	13 June	4.4	4.4	5.7	5.8	5.0
	12	23 June	3.3	3.4	5.4	5.7	4.7
Susceptible ^d	30	13 June	5.8	6.1	7.3	7.2	6.6
	10	13 June	5.7	5.4	7.0	7.1	6.3
Overall mean	100	13 June	4.8	4.8	6.1	6.1	5.4
	56	13 June	2.9	2.8	4.6	4.8	3.9
LAC23 (check)	6	23 June	2.7	3.0	4.5	5.0	3.8

^aScale of 1 to 9.

^bScore: 1–3.

^cScore: 4–6.

^dScore: 7–9.

LAC23, IRAT 13, FT 34061, Mahadampai, C 168-134, Pinilot 330, Payamult, IR2035-108-2, IR2733-F5B-6-4, IR2151-957-5-3, IR3276-3, T16, TOS 2300, H4, and the

locally bred upland lines LS(1)-5-2, LS(1)-7, LS(24)-6-NI 2, LS(24)-6-NI 3, TOX 95-8-1-1-LA 5, TOX 95-8-14-NI 7, TOX 95-8-1-5-NI 4, and TOX 159-2-1-1-LS1.

Occurrence of *Cercospora* leaf spot disease of rice in Pakistan

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Cercospora leaf spot, usually known as narrow brown leaf spot and caused by *Cercospora oryzae*, was observed for the first time in Pakistan at the Rice Research Institute, Dokri, in the International Rice Yield Nursery of the International Rice Testing Program. The nursery was planted during the 1977 kharif.

The fungus usually attacked the leaves, but, in severe cases of infection, also attacked the grains. Reddish to blackish-brown streaks were produced on the leaves, and, in some cases, also yellow margins and brownish-grey center. The spots had a linear appearance and were parallel to the leaf veins. They varied from 3 to 22 mm in length and from 1 to 4 mm in breadth.

Entries with the best resistance to both leaf and grain infection, with ratings

of less than 4, were TNAU13471, C038, IET5656, IETS854, IET2911, MTU8431, MTU9416, BKN6987-128-2-4, IR579.

The incidence of the disease is not regarded as serious at present, but a keen watch is necessary to check its spread.

Reaction of certain promising rice selections to tungro virus disease

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A field trial to evaluate 14 promising rices for resistance to rice tungro virus was conducted during the 1977–78 pishanam season (Dec.–March). Tungro incidence at the maximum tillering stage was recorded with the standard evaluation method used at IRRI.

Rice tungro virus incidence was comparatively lower in AS2422, AS5250, AS5272, AS3827, AS1391, and AS4003

(see table). AS2572, AS2690, AS2686, AS651, and AS5284 were found moderately resistant; AS3699, AS3704, and AS3799 were susceptible. The tungro-resistant rices may be used in breeding programs.

Reaction of promising rice cultures to tungro virus disease. Tamil Nadu, India.

Rice culture	Parentage	Disease incidence (%)
AS3821	IR26/IR22	1.8
AS2512	AD9588/ADT30	11.9
AS2686	Sel. from RP533-200-2-2-1-1	9.3
AS2690	Sel. from RP533-200-2-2-1-5	11.1
AS3704	ADT31/Culture 198	28.0
AS5391	ASD 14/Ratna	3.5
AS5272	ASD 8/IR8	1.6
AS3699	ADT31/Culture 198	58.1
AS4003	ASD 7/AS 2	4.5
AS2422	ASD 14/IR127	1.2
AS5250	ASD 8/IR8	1.4
AS3199	IR26/CR 106-90	38.0
AS5284	ADT31/Ratna	11.1
AS651	ASD 5/IR8	8.7